

From paper to practice: how reform design shapes implementation

Anna Malandrino, Maria Tullia Galanti & Giovanni Barbato

To cite this article: Anna Malandrino, Maria Tullia Galanti & Giovanni Barbato (23 May 2025): From paper to practice: how reform design shapes implementation, Policy Design and Practice, DOI: [10.1080/25741292.2025.2498257](https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2025.2498257)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2025.2498257>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group.

Published online: 23 May 2025.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

Article views: 35

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

From paper to practice: how reform design shapes implementation

Anna Malandrino^a

^aUniversità degli Studi di Torino, Torino, Italy; ^bUniversità degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy

ABSTRACT

This article investigates how the design of policy reforms can influence their implementation, analyzing the case of initial teacher education and training (ITET) reforms in Italy. It addresses the following question: To what extent can the design of policy reforms, as codified in legal texts, help explain subsequent implementation failures? Building on a framework that draws together insights from the policy evaluation literature and the policy analysis literature, it focuses on three key dimensions of design as reflected in legal texts: precision, internal coherence, and external coherence. The framework is applied to a within-case comparison of five major ITET reforms enacted between 1989 and 2019. The study, conducted through qualitative text analysis and process tracing, reveals how unclear policy goals, internal inconsistencies between objectives and instruments, and especially misalignment with recruitment systems as well as financial and administrative capacities undermine implementation. By bridging evaluation and design perspectives, the article offers an *ex ante* approach to understanding how policies-as-written can anticipate implementation failures.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 2 February 2024

Accepted 18 April 2025

KEYWORDS

Policy design; implementation failure; ex-ante evaluation; process tracing; administrative capacity; education policy; Italy

1. Introduction

All too often, the connection between the design and implementation phases remains hidden in the formulation phase. Still, the way policies are designed through primary or secondary legislation shapes subsequent phases, especially in contexts where the law represents one of the main vehicles of policy change through reform of both the goals and the instruments of a policy. This article examines how specific features of reform design may help explain implementation outcomes and discusses how an analytical framework that brings together policy evaluation and policy analysis insights can support policymakers in identifying design-related risks *ex ante*.

CONTACT Maria Tullia Galanti Università degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy.

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group.

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

To do so, the article analyzes initial teacher education and training (ITET) reforms in Italy by bridging the design and the evaluation literature. It does so in light of the policy concept framework (PCF), which employs criteria such as the precision, internal coherence, and external coherence of a reform as developed on paper (Sager et al. 2015), and further developing it in light of the literature on design “as a noun” (Howlett and Rayner 2013, 171). In doing so, it connects the evaluation literature, from where the PCF derives, and the policy analysis literature, by emphasizing how the precision and coherence of a reform and how they relate to implementation dynamics can be anticipated through the analysis of legal text.

The analytical framework underpinned by these criteria is applied to the Italian ITET case to show how an appropriate design is a key component for the correct functioning of policy programs in the implementation phase, and how vice versa policy implementation issues can be rooted in poor policy design (Virani et al. 2024). Italian ITET reforms offer an interesting within-case comparison to better understand how policies-as-written (Fowler 2021) can anticipate implementation problems, given the paramount importance that legal instruments have in reform in most civil law countries with Continental or Napoleonic administrative systems, where written laws and regulations play an eminent role in driving the work of the bureaucracies and in governmentality (Regonini 2017).

Hence, the article contributes to bridging the gap between policy evaluation and policy design by operationalizing a set of *ex ante* criteria for assessing reform quality. It offers a novel application of the PCF to a longitudinal case of education reform, with implications for both researchers and practitioners. The article addresses the following research question: To what extent can the design of policy reforms, as codified in legal texts, help explain subsequent implementation failures?

The paper is organized as follows: the *Analytical framework* section (Section 2) introduces the criteria used to assess reform design, drawing on both policy evaluation and policy analysis literatures. The *Research design* section (Section 3) outlines the case selection and methodological approach. The *ITET reform design* section applies the framework to five major Italian reforms. The *ITET reform implementation and related issues* section discusses how design shortcomings affected implementation. Finally, *Discussion and conclusions* reflect on the broader implications for policy design and reform governance.

2. Analytical framework

According to the PCF, criteria to assess reforms as developed on paper include the evidence use, precision, internal coherence, and external coherence underlying a reform as developed on paper (Sager et al. 2015). These criteria contribute to a rational study of policy design “as a noun,” as they build relevant policy knowledge to be used “for the crafting of alternative possible courses of action intended to address specific policy problems” (Howlett and Rayner 2013, 171) and compatible with the existing policy context. These criteria provide a heuristic to analyze policy design as a noun, i.e. the logic through which policy intends to achieve its goals (Schneider and Ingram 1988). Policy design as a noun differs from policy design as a verb as the former captures the essence of policies-as-written (Fowler 2021),

while the latter captures the processual nature of the formulation stage (Capano and Malandrino 2022), and is described as “an activity which unfolds in the policy process as policy actors deliberate and interact over the construction of both the means or mechanisms through which policy goals are given effect and the goals of policy themselves” (Howlett and Rayner 2013, 170). While the procedural characteristics of a reform—including the use of evidence—are not of interest for the present work, the PCF allows for a pragmatic operationalization of classical evaluation theories such as Weiss’s (1997) theory of change to achieve a different goal, i.e. design assessment for predictive purposes.

In principle, we adopt Weiss’s view of policy programs as a sequence of causes and effects: for instance, a program that trains prospective teachers expects them to gain practical skills; with skills, teachers become authoritative as professionals; authoritativeness and skills together make them credible, reliable teachers. However, our approach differs from Weiss’s in that her evaluation is built on collecting data to see how well each step of the sequence actually worked (*ex post*), while our assessment rather focuses on those dimensions of a program that can help us, *ex ante*, to predict how the program will be implemented. In doing so, we bring together two policy literatures, namely the evaluation one, which has an *ex post* approach (and to which the PCF itself belongs), and the policy analysis literature, which embraces an *ex ante* approach and in this article dialogues with evaluation criteria by interpreting and applying them as design assessment criteria. In doing this, our approach shares with evaluation literature the search for generalization, while keeping in mind that innumerable variables impact how a program works and thus refraining from any deterministic conclusion.

Our assessment of a reform as it appears “on paper” in legislative documents focuses on substantive dimensions that offer the opportunity to operationalize policy design “as a noun.” While we acknowledge the importance of the use of evidence as a criterion to distinguish “‘better’ or more ‘intelligent’ designs’ from ‘poor’ designs, and from ‘non-designs’” (Howlett and Rayner 2013, 172; also Capano 2018), at the same time we recognize that data about the use of evidence are seldom detectable from the written texts of laws and regulations, especially in countries where policymaking has a strong legal connotation (Parkhurst 2017; Regonini 2017).

Therefore, the first criterion for our assessment of reform design as it appears on paper concerns *precision*, understood as the accuracy of the program objectives all the way to the intended effects (Sager et al. 2015, 98). Precision captures the presence in reforms of policy objectives articulated in terms of concrete policy instruments, timelines, and possibly measurable indicators. Hence, precision allows us to evaluate policy success against objective benchmarks and provides clear route guidance for policy implementers while leaving the latter with a reasonable amount of discretion (Malandrino and Sager 2021). Although it is true that not all goals must be measurable and that some goals can serve hortatory purposes (Schneider and Ingram 1988), in our framework the precision criterion concerns the use, beyond aspirational declared goals, of elements useful for guiding policy implementation. While much of the policy implementation debate has centered on top-down versus bottom-up perspectives (Fowler 2021), the relevance of precision in policy design draws on a long-standing debate within the implementation literature, including in

those models that aim to reconcile these two traditions (Matland 1995). Sabatier and Mazmanian (1980) argue that clearly defined policy objectives, targets, and detailed procedural guidelines reduce ambiguity, thereby enhancing the likelihood of effective implementation by limiting divergent interpretations among implementing actors. Similarly, Matland (1995) highlights that policy ambiguity often creates uncertainty and conflict during implementation, hampering the realization of intended policy outcomes. More recently, Fowler (2021) finds that ambiguity and uncertainty remain critical challenges in policy implementation, as varying interpretations among stakeholders can lead to divergent outcomes.

The second criterion, i.e. *internal coherence*, refers to the avoidance of internal contradictions in the program logic (Howlett and Rayner 2007, 7) and pertains to how policy instruments match policy goals and program objectives as declared on paper (Howlett et al. 2014). Goals and instruments in ITET reforms are mostly linked by means of a mix of normative and technical assumptions regarding the relationship between goals and target behavior (Schneider and Ingram 1988). For example, prospective teachers are expected to engage in a certain number of traineeship hours both because the school system needs experienced teachers (normative assumption) and because the traineeship is directly linked to the acquisition of hands-on competences by those prospective teachers (technical assumption).

The third criterion concerns *external coherence*, i.e. the extent to which a reform is compatible with its external policy context. This context consists of the other policies in place in adjacent policy domains and the available administrative and financial capacity. The evolution and/or adaptation of the policy under examination and of the adjacent policies can influence—by improving or worsening it—the overall coherence of the former with its context and the resources at the government's disposal (Howlett and Rayner 2013, 172).

We argue that an adequate reform design (as a noun) in light of our three assessment criteria is able to anticipate and prevent implementation failures (Sager et al. 2015).

Precision avoids leaving excessive discretion to the implementation stage while setting a clear background against which implementation can operate. While timelines and procedures may be set either by primary or secondary legislation, their existence and clear formulation are core elements to regulate the action of implementers (Schneider and Ingram 1988). At the same time, precision allows achieving a first assessment of the characteristics of the micro-design of policy reforms, which describes how the policy instruments should work in practice (Capano and Howlett 2024).

Internal coherence provides the basis for solid measures that are well-balanced and adequate to pursue the specific policy objectives of each reform, also contributing to a more fine-grained understanding of the micro design. In this regard, Sabatier and Mazmanian (1980) highlight how a flawed causal theory is problematic for successful implementation due to the misalignment between means and ends.

Through external coherence, the examined reforms communicate with other adjacent, related policies, thus making it possible to activate necessary synergies at the implementation stage. Indeed, taken together, internal and external coherence build the necessary consistency that is a requirement for policy implementation.

This determines the policy's ability to maximize complementary relationships while mitigating incompatibility between policy elements (which for instance could trigger contradictory responses from program targets) as well as its feasibility and goodness of fit with the existing policy capacity and governance structure (Howlett et al. 2014). Feasibility, in turn, also implies coherence with the available resources, in terms of both funding and administrative capacity.

Finally, while our framework focuses on how precision, internal coherence and external coherence shape implementation outcomes, we acknowledge that additional factors—such as political dynamics and stakeholder coordination—can also influence policy implementation (Fowler 2021; Matland 1995; Sabatier and Mazmanian 1980). Introducing these alternative explanations allows for a more comprehensive understanding of how policy design interacts with broader systemic conditions, while reinforcing the need to consider both structural design features and contextual variables when assessing policy implementation.

3. Research design

The article employs a within-case comparison of different ITET schemes, intended as design “objects,” to carry out a theory-based assessment of the main ITET reforms in Italy over the last thirty years, and to offer some reflection about the potential impact of how a reform is written “on paper” and the implementation gaps experienced.

3.1. Case selection

Our units of analysis are the different ITET reforms as developed on paper, particularly the ITET schemes described by primary and secondary legislations approved by Italian central governments from 1989 to 2019, which all together account for a complex maze of policies characterized by continuous layering (Malandrino 2021): SFP, SSIS, TFA, FIT, PF24 (Table 1). In Italy, ITET policies are the responsibility of the central government, which defines education and training requirements for prospective teachers in the public education system. These ITET schemes combine distinct sets of policy goals and instruments designed to enhance teacher preparation across various levels of the school system. Since the 1990s, the Italian ITET system has been structured along two main schemes: a concurrent one for aspiring primary school teachers, which requires a specific master's degree including both theoretical education and practical training; and a consecutive one, where aspiring secondary school teachers with master's degrees in specific fields move to professional training in a successive phase (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice 2021).

ITET is both highly salient—given the high number of public employees in the school system—and controversial, due to competing views on what constitutes effective teacher preparation and how ITET systems should be structured. Moreover, the Italian system provides multiple ITET reform cases due to frequent scheme changes, which allows for comparison within a relatively short timeframe. Nonetheless, the analysis of Italian ITET reforms offers insights that are highly relevant beyond the national context. First, as in other European countries (Garritzmann and

Table 1. Examined reforms with main implementation issues.

Government	Primary and secondary legislation	Name of ITET scheme	Main policy content of the ITET scheme	Implementation issues
Andreotti (1989–1991) Prodi (1996–1998)	Law 341/1990; MD 153/1998	Scuola di Specializzazione all’Insegnamento Secondario (SSIS)	Postgraduate two-year school for secondary teaching	Differentiated activation throughout the country (Tammaro et al. 2017)
	Law 341/1990; MD 153/1998	Scienze della Formazione Primaria (SFP)	Master’s degree program in Primary Education Sciences	No central monitoring (Cappa et al. 2013) Little coordination with recruitment (Magni 2019)
Berlusconi (2008–2011) Monti (2011–2013)	Law 133/2008; MD 249/2010; MD 81/2013	Tirocinio Formativo Attivo (TFA)	Postgraduate one-year training and education path	No central coordination and differentiated activation (Tammaro et al. 2017) Failure to activate teaching-specific master’s programs (Magni 2019)
Renzi (2014–2016) Gentiloni (2016–2018)	Law 107/2015; D.Lgs. 59/2017; MD 616/2017	Formazione Iniziale e Tirocinio (FIT)	Gradually paid three-year training and education path	Incomplete implementation (Magni 2019)
Conte (2018–2019)	Law 145/2018	Percorso di Formazione 24 crediti (PF24)	System based on an unstructured acquisition of 24 ECTS credits	Delays in recruitment procedures (due to Covid-19 pandemic) Universities as “exam factories” (Benvenuto 2023)

Source: authors’ elaboration.

Garrizmann 2023), the school system is characterized by a “bureaucratic-professional” governance model where ministerial officials and teachers’ trade unions are highly influential in policy design, and legislative reforms activate political conflict over policy instruments (Capano and Lippi 2018; Galanti 2023). Second, ITET reforms involve interdependencies between policy domains—school education, personnel recruitment, budget, and higher education—making it relevant to address the interplay between design features and wider policy coherence (Howlett and Rayner 2013).

Assessing ITET reforms is crucial, as these policies affect teacher quality and quantity (Musset 2010) and, consequently, the quality of education provided, leading policymakers to pay increasing attention to them (Symeonidis 2018). Focusing on ITET allows us to understand how it is framed and interpreted by policy designers, and how poorly designed policies may contribute to policy failure (Virani et al. 2024). Assessing ITET reform design involves a multifaceted analysis of various elements predicted to impact implementation. Among these is the extent to which policy designers provide clear guidance for policy implementation, define the desired profile of the prospective teacher, and calibrate the provisions that establish the organization, length, and effort required for teacher training, as well as the compatibility of the ITET design with the external policy context.

3.2. Data collection and analysis

The examined data sources consist of legislative texts for the design-as-a-noun analysis and education-specific literature, together with selected press and

education portal contents, for the implementation analysis. In addition, we consulted policy discussion records, policy documents, and specialized press and grey literature. The analysis of reform design is based on a qualitative textual analysis of legislative documents, aimed at identifying the presence or absence of key design features corresponding to the three criteria outlined in the analytical framework. This involved close reading and coding of legal texts—both primary and secondary legislation—according to operational indicators of precision, internal coherence, and external coherence (see [Supplementary material, Table S1](#)). This approach treats legal texts not only as formal outputs of policymaking, but as structured representations of policy logic that can be systematically examined to anticipate implementation trajectories, which were examined through process tracing.

4. ITET reforms as designed: a text-based analysis

4.1. Precision

To analyze the precision of SFP and SSIS, we first need to look at Law 341/1990. The law does not contain explicit reference to the expected outcomes of SFP and SSIS, delegating them to secondary legislation. Relevant secondary legislation (Ministerial Decree 153) was first issued in 1998. It concerned the organization of SFP and SSIS and detailed criteria regarding learning goals, content, activities, and length of primary and secondary school ITET. These elements reveal a medium-to-high level of precision for SFP and SSIS.

The next schemes were based on a clearer definition and greater importance of the traineeship. TFA was designed after the decision to rationalize public expenditure by downsizing schools' personnel, terminating SSIS in 2009. MD 249/2010 set explicit goals, defined ITET instruments, and anticipated a monitoring and evaluation system, displaying a high level of precision.

The idea to combine education with a “hands-on” traineeship inspired FIT, introduced with Law 107/2015, aimed at realizing cultural and social appreciation of teaching through the endowment of teachers with professional and financially sustainable training. The Law established that ITET involve universities and be coordinated with recruitment. Legislative decree 59/2017 further specified reform goals, innovations, and requirements. The level of precision in terms of goals and expectations was high, but the law lacked specific information regarding the implementation timeline. For these reasons, the precision level can be considered medium.

PF24 stemmed from the need to rationalize expenditure for personnel recruitment. This motivation aimed at solving problems related to fixed-term teaching contracts and the lack of qualified teachers. The law established a system simplifying recruitment through public competitions. Aspiring teachers needed a master's degree and 24 ECTS credits in specific disciplines. PF24 amounted to an unstructured acquisition of credits for prospective teachers (Benvenuto 2023). The precision level is medium-to-low, as no clear ITET objectives were defined, although rules for accessing the teaching profession were overall clear.

4.2. Internal coherence

Our analysis of internal coherence assesses the consistency of each training path in terms of the amount of training and education (number of ECTS credits) and coherence of the designed ITET scheme with the declared policy objectives.

The first subdimension (Table 2) looks at ECTS credits and the training's expected duration as a proxy for their coherence with teacher preparation goals, assuming that other things equal, more ECTS credits mean more teacher knowledge. In this regard, the establishment of SSIS represented an absolute novelty since, before, no pre-service training was provided for secondary school teachers. In this regard, the coherence of SSIS was certainly remarkable. Subsequently, the number of credits provided by each reform decreased significantly, culminating with the abolition of FIT and the dismantling of almost any trace of pre-service training by reducing postgraduate ITET to only 24 credits – among the shortest in Europe (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice 2021). At the primary school level, the establishment of SFP definitively placed ITET in the university sphere. Previously, primary school teachers were only required to be trained at the secondary education level. Hence, SFP carried a particularly high coherence compared to the previous training system. With MD 249/2010, SFP was extended to five years but remained essentially unchanged in its training goals and content.

Table 2 provides an overview of ITET training paths in terms of ECTS credits and years of duration, offering a comparative perspective on the intensity of teacher preparation across different reforms. The table highlights variations in training length and credit distribution, allowing for an assessment of how each reform structured teacher education requirements over time.

The second analytical dimension pertains to the coherence of the ITET schemes, as a combination of theoretical and practical activities, with the specific policy objectives declared. While the general goal of any ITET scheme is to have “better” teachers, policymakers may have in mind a specific balance between theoretical education and practical training for specific policy goals.

The ITET schemes designed by the 1990 reform aimed to achieve both cultural and professional training for teachers, anticipating equal importance for theoretical and practical activities. For SFP programs, the balance slightly favored theoretical training, considering that SFP students/trainees came directly from high school and needed theoretical grounding before professional training. SSIS (for aspiring

Table 2. ITET paths in terms of ECTS credits and years.

Scheme	ECTS credits	Years	Coherence
Primary school			
SFP Berlinguer (graduate)	240	4	High
SFP Gelmini (graduate)	300	5	High
Secondary school			
SSIS (postgraduate)	120	2	High
TFA (postgraduate)	60	1	Medium
FIT (postgraduate)	24 (access) + 60 (first year) + 15 (second year) = 75	3	High
PF24 (graduate/postgraduate) ¹	24	<1	Low

Source: authors' elaboration from policy documents.

secondary school teachers) was accessible only to graduate students, with balanced theoretical and practical training.

TFA aimed to qualify and value the teaching profession through subject-based and cross-sectoral competencies, emphasizing hands-on training. However, the percentage of credits for theoretical education (63%) was significantly higher than practical training (37%), signaling low internal coherence. Practical training was disconnected from theoretical training. The initial TFA idea was to enhance practical training through a traineeship in the school classroom with a “tutor” teacher.

FIT aimed to simplify the professional training system for better social appreciation of the teaching profession, anticipating a prevalence of practical training. FIT was a three-year program accessible through a public competition. Theoretical education would prevail only in the first year, while practical training was connected to teacher recruitment through fixed-term paid contracts.

PF24 was meant to rationalize expenditure for personnel recruitment and make savings, without clarifying the expected education-training balance. The related 2018 reform repealed the FIT path, saving only the acquisition of 24 credits in psycho-pedagogical, anthropological, and teaching methodologies subjects. The balance was completely skewed toward theoretical education, although we cannot assess this design against any explicit educational objective.

Table 3 examines the internal coherence of ITET schemes by comparing the declared policy goals regarding the balance between theoretical education and practical training with the actual distribution of ECTS credits. This comparison sheds light on whether the designed ITET schemes aligned with their intended objectives.

4.3. External coherence

In the ITET schemes developed in the Nineties, higher education policies played a crucial role in professionalizing teacher training. Concurrently, HE reform led to greater didactic autonomy for Italian universities (Capano 2018). These parallel transformations are vital for the external coherence of ITET reforms. ITET policies were moving toward uniformity in preparing Italian school teachers. With SFP, primary school teachers would no longer be divided between those with optional university studies and those with only a high school diploma. With SSIS, secondary school teachers would need both graduate subject-related and postgraduate didactic preparation. While all Italian teachers now required university preparation, the university

Table 3. Coherence of ITET schemes with declared policy objectives.

Scheme	Declared policy goals in terms of education-training balance	Theoretical education (% ECTS credits)	Practical training (% ECTS credits)	Internal coherence
SFP (Berlinguer)	Theoretical education = Practical training	70%	30%	High
SSIS		55%	45%	High
SFP (Gelmini)	Practical training > Theoretical education	87%	13%	Low
TFA		63%	37%	High
FIT: first year	Practical training > Theoretical education	73%	27%	Medium
FIT: second and third years		0%	100%	
PF24	Not declared	100%	0%	NA

Source: authors' elaboration.

system reform granted institutions significant autonomy, necessitating effective coordination and monitoring to ensure uniform teacher preparation (Cappa et al. 2013).

At the beginning of the XXI century, most five-year degree programs were replaced with three-year programs followed by two-year specialized degrees. SFP remained a four-year program, while SSIS added two years of education to the $3+2=5$ years for a master's degree, totaling 7 years for aspiring secondary teachers. The SFP exception constituted an initial misalignment with the new arrangement, and SSIS faced criticism for its length, prompting alternative proposals (Pupolin 2000). However, SSIS aligned with the modular approach to university studies, offering choice points at the three-year degree, master's degree, and SSIS levels. However, a key design issue was the lack of a mechanism for coordination with the recruitment system regarding available positions.

The reform that transformed SFP into a five-year program and established TFA maintained the ITET difference between primary and secondary school teachers despite affirming teaching's unitary nature (MD 249/2010, Art. 2(3)). Aspiring primary school teachers had to attend a five-year single-cycle degree program, while aspiring secondary teachers followed a $3+2+1$ model: a three-year bachelor's program, a two-year master's program, and a one-year TFA. The MD stipulated that trainee numbers should be coordinated with actual recruitment needs (Art.5(2)). However, the reform did not recognize the habilitation demands of those with teaching experience; hence, a clash materialized between TFA and PAS (*percorso abilitante speciale*), also called "special TFA," a simplified TFA without traineeship or entry test for teachers with three years of prior teaching service.

An attempt to reconcile ITET policies with recruitment policies came with the (never fully implemented) FIT. Access to FIT required 24 ECTS credits in anthropological, psychological, pedagogical, and didactic disciplines. The objectives and contents were defined centrally, leaving universities little room for maneuver, but appeared consistent with the principle of uniformity of essential service performance levels. The reform provided a national coordination and monitoring system (Conferenza nazionale per la formazione iniziale e l'accesso alla professione docente), later suppressed. It unified ITET and recruitment into an organic path, although some pedagogist literature argues these should remain distinct (Magni 2019). FIT's gradually paid design introduced a novelty, as prospective teachers would be paid, instead of paying for ITET. The FIT reform was designed as a highly structured and financially demanding three-year system. However, due to budget constraints and a lack of administrative capacity, it was ultimately repealed by a more simple and inexpensive system.

Beyond considerations of the minimal PF24 pathway's value, we observe a degree of linearity between PF24 and recruitment, resulting from the extreme simplification of ITET for financial reasons. The PF24 requirements enabled preparation uniformity throughout the country, given their detailed and centralized definition inherited from the previous reform, while compelling universities to adapt.

5. From design to delivery: unpacking the implementation of ITET reforms

The implementation of ITET reforms has been influenced by their design characteristics, underscoring how inadequate planning can lead to operational challenges.

The specificity of these reforms varied over time, contributing to diverse policy implementation issues. These can be especially traced back to design issues concerning external incoherence and, to a lesser extent, internal coherence and precision.

5.1. Internal incoherence, imprecision, and implementation challenges

The internal coherence of the examined reforms has often been compromised by discrepancies between objectives and instruments. The TFA aimed to enhance practical training; however, its structure resulted in a predominance of theoretical education, with 63% of credits allocated to theory, thereby hindering the effectiveness of the practical component. Similarly, the PF24 (Percorso Formativo 24 CFU), essentially intended to streamline expenses, created a minimalistic and unstructured training path, depriving prospective teachers of substantial practical preparation. These inconsistencies, significant from an educational point of view, did not directly affect reform implementation, although they were employed (especially in the case of PF24) as ground for subsequent further reform. Instead, where we can see a clear impact of design on implementation is firstly the lack of an efficient ministerial coordination mechanism for TFA traineeships throughout the country (Cappa et al. 2013), which ended up affecting their implementation and hence their professionalizing value (Tammaro et al. 2017). Likewise, the lack of a supervisory body in charge of the SSIS implementation dampened the innovative thrust of SSIS, and in particular its focus on balancing theoretical and practical training (Cappa et al. 2013). Hence, based on our analysis, the provision of these mechanisms/bodies for supervision and coordination proved to be an essential design element to be assessed under the internal coherence criterion. As for precision, its lack was essentially relevant in the case of FIT. Here, the absence of provisions regarding the expected timeline for scheme implementation was detrimental to the scheme, which was never completely implemented.

5.2. The role of external (in)coherence in shaping implementation outcomes

According to our analysis, the most substantial inconsistencies that led to implementation issues can be observed at the external coherence level, with reforms lacking integration with recruitment policies, university capacities, and available administrative and financial capacities. The discontinuation of the FIT, for example, was driven by economic sustainability concerns, demonstrating how incompatibility with available resources can undermine the implementation of a theoretically sound system. The same occurred with PF24, whose lack of external coherence with the rationale of academic preparation was particularly striking—in this regard, commentators noted how with this reform, universities were reduced to the mere role of “*esamifici*” (exam factories) (Benvenuto 2023, 18). The gradually paid design of FIT introduced a novelty into the ITET landscape because, for the first time, prospective teachers would be paid instead of paying for ITET; but its incompatibility with spending review goals as underscored by the next reform (which repealed it) led to its failed implementation—a proper FIT path, indeed, was never finalized.

In the case of TFA, the pitfalls in its design and specifically the lack of adequate consideration for experienced non-tenured teachers led to the establishment of a “transitional” TFA, which remained the only TFA ever implemented. This in turn came into conflict with the poor technical capacity of the ministerial bureaucracies, which would go so far as to apologize for the formulation of imprecise and ambiguous questions in the access tests (Magni 2019). From a different perspective, the high number of *abilitati* (qualified candidates) created by the “privileged” path would hardly be compatible with the actual recruitment needs. Moreover, besides constituting an internal coherence issue, the lack of central coordination of TFAs was also an external coherence problem as it determined delays in the activation of traineeships causing friction between schools and universities (Tammaro et al. 2017). After all, according to the related normative text, TFA was to be accessed upon possession of a specific master’s degree whose related programs would have to be established within the Italian university system, an event that never materialized due to the lack of consideration of the universities’ difficulties inherent in carrying out a hasty didactic reorganization process, combined with the political instability that would shortly lead to a new ITET reform.²

Going back to the SSIS reform, the lack of an efficient coordination mechanism with the recruitment system facilitated the repeal of SSIS because it made it easy for the new, different-color government to label it as a source of precarious work due to the activation of more SSIS positions than those available for recruitment and the lack of regularly launched public competitions for accessing the profession. The closure of SSIS, however, generated further contradictions: a decision contained in an early version of decree-law (DL) 137/2008 determined the exclusion of last-(ninth)-SSIS-cycle graduates from the lists used (inter alia) for permanent recruitment, which caused the unions’ protests; the Ministry later remedied this issue through an amendment that readmitted last-cycle SSIS graduates.

6. Discussion and conclusions

Our analysis shows that reform design, and especially external incoherence, contribute to explaining implementation failures. The previous sections demonstrate how specific design issues affected all examined reforms and their implementation. These include the poor definition of expected outcomes, lack of implementation timelines, non-provision of central coordination mechanisms, disconnect between policy objectives and measures, and incompatibilities with adjacent policy domains, resources and capacities.

Imprecise legislation led to more detail delegation to the regulatory phase, sometimes resulting in necessary measures not being adopted. Fluctuating internal incoherence and external coherence issues contributed to counterproductive stratification of inconsistent reforms, unfit to achieve intended goals (Capano 2019). Phenomena like never-activated teaching-specific master’s programs or non-activation of the three-year FIT stem from reform design. The same applies to coordination with recruitment needs, indicating a detachment between adjacent policy domains that could have been addressed at the design level. Reform design

also created tensions between actors, such as schools and universities, due to the difficult joint organization of traineeships without a coordination system (Tammaro et al. 2017).

These issues should be considered and addressed when carrying out the delicate task of designing reforms. The findings point to a set of priorities that should inform the design of future reforms:

- Increase precision at the legislative level, particularly regarding boundaries and implementation timelines, rather than delegating to the regulatory level, as a necessary means to avoid inaction and secure coordination mechanisms between actors involved in implementation.
- Strengthen internal coherence by explicating the link between desired goals and measurable outcomes, to understand how different ITET paths affect teacher preparation quality. The reform design must provide a stable data monitoring system and benefit from the possibility to assess teachers' preparation comparatively, as well as implementation coordination mechanisms.
- As for external coherence, policymakers must adapt policy instruments to their environment, including available resources and capacities as well as adjacent policy domains—particularly recruitment—in addition to temporary circumstances like pandemics or economic crises.
- Policy change and innovation take time. Policymakers should refrain from frequently dismantling the ITET system. A reform trajectory that constantly shifts course risks circling back on itself rather than moving forward. The instability of the ITET system was compounded by political turnovers, with each new coalition leveraging the perceived failures of previous reforms as a rationale for introducing new ones. This instability led to prospective teachers having to continuously adapt to comply with changing requirements, which created uncertainty and opacity (Argentin and Giancola 2013). For aspiring teachers, frequent changes in ITET paths are costly, implying continuous investment in compulsory training to meet new requirements. More generally, early implementation of reforms always carries transition issues related to adapting to a new system (Malandrino 2022); avoiding continual removal and replacement of ITET paths can help consolidate adopted instruments and pay off “transition costs.”

While our findings reveal significant design flaws within the Italian ITET reforms, they do not simply represent a localized pathology. Instead, these issues—such as imprecise timelines, weak coordination mechanisms, and misaligned internal and external coherence—could be symptomatic of broader challenges inherent in bureaucratic-professional systems. Consequently, we postulate that reforms crafted with greater precision, internal coherence and especially a stronger coherence between reform texts, adjacent policy domains and available resources and capacities have higher chances of success. These patterns call for further investigation across institutional and policy settings, to assess the extent to which design features can help account for implementation success in complex governance systems.

Notes

1. As ECTS credits can be obtained during or after the graduate-level path.
2. See meeting of Italian Rectors' Conference (CRUI), 28 April 2011.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Funding

The authors acknowledge support from the University of Milan through the APC initiative and from the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research, project Prin 2017, 'Who advises what, when and how? Policy analysis capacity and its impact on Italian policymaking', 2017WMW433.

ORCID

Anna Malandrino <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-3643-9600>

Maria Tullia Galanti <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-1984-9085>

Giovanni Barbato <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4209-6464>

References

- Argentin, G., and O. Giancola. 2013. "Diventare Insegnanti in Europa. Una Comparazione Tra Quattro Paesi." *Scuola Democratica* 3: 863–877.
- Benvenuto, G. 2023. "Lezioni Dal Passato. Cosa (Non) ha Funzionato Nella Formazione Degli Insegnanti? Costruire il Futuro: le Emergenze Dalla Ricerca per la Formazione." *Lifelong Lifewide Learning* 19 (42): 14–24.
- Capano, G. 2018. "Policy Design Spaces in Reforming Governance in Higher Education: The Dynamics in Italy and The Netherlands." *Higher Education* 75 (4): 675–694. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10734-017-0158-5>.
- Capano, G. 2019. "Reconceptualizing Layering—From Mode of Institutional Change to Mode of Institutional Design: Types and Outputs." *Public Administration* 97 (3): 590–604. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12583>.
- Capano, G., and A. Lippi. 2018. "How Decision-Makers Make the 'Right Choice'? Instrument Selection between Legitimacy and Instrumentality: Evidence from Education Policy in Italy (1996-2016)." *Rivista Italiana di Politiche Pubbliche* 13(2): 219–254.
- Capano, G., and M. Howlett. 2024. "Calibration and Specification in Policy Practice: Micro-Dimensions of Policy Design." *Policy Design and Practice* 7 (2): 115–128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2024.2353929>.
- Capano, G., and A. Malandrino. 2022. "Mapping the Use of Knowledge in Policymaking: barriers and Facilitators from a Subjectivist Perspective (1990–2020)." *Policy Sciences* 55 (3): 399–428. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-022-09468-0>.
- Cappa, C., O. Niceforo, and D. Palomba. 2013. "La Formazione Iniziale Degli Insegnanti in Italia." *Revista Española de Educación Comparada* 0 (22): 139–163. <https://doi.org/10.5944/reec.22.2013.9327>.
- European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice. 2021. *Teachers in Europe: Careers, Development and Well-Being. Eurydice Report*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.
- Fowler, L. 2021. "How to Implement Policy: Coping with Ambiguity and Uncertainty." *Public Administration* 99 (3): 581–597. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12702>.

- Galanti, M. T. 2023. "Expert Legitimacy and Competing Legitimation in Italian School Reforms." *Policy and Society* 42 (3): 288–302. <https://doi.org/10.1093/polsoc/puad024>.
- Garritzmann, J. L., and S. Garritzmann. 2023. "Why Globalization Hardly Affects Education Systems: A Historical Institutional View." Mattei et al. (eds.) *The Oxford Handbook of Education and Globalization*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Howlett, M., I. Mukherjee, and J. Rayner. 2014. "The Elements of Effective Program Design: A Two-Level Analysis." *Politics and Governance* 2 (2): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.v2i2.23>.
- Howlett, M., and J. Rayner. 2007. "Design Principles for Policy Mixes: Cohesion and Coherence in 'New Governance Arrangements.'" *Policy and Society* 26 (4): 1–18. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1449-4035\(07\)70118-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1449-4035(07)70118-2).
- Howlett, M., and J. Rayner. 2013. "Patching vs Packaging in Policy Formulation: Assessing Policy Portfolio Design." *Politics and Governance* 1 (2): 170–182. <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.v1i2.95>.
- Magni, F. 2019. *Formazione Iniziale e Reclutamento Degli Insegnanti in Italia*. Rome: Edizioni Studium.
- Malandrino, A. 2021. "Le Politiche per la Formazione Iniziale Degli Insegnanti e L'accesso Alla Professione in Italia: caratteristiche e Criticità Alla Luce Dell'institutional Layering." *Rivista Italiana di Politiche Pubbliche* 16 (2): 161–190.
- Malandrino, A. 2022. "Lonely": education Policies and Their Reception, between Indigestible Carrots and Demands for Proper Regulation." *Contemporary Italian Politics* 14 (2): 275–288. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23248823.2022.2061116>.
- Malandrino, A., and F. Sager. 2021. "Can Teachers' Discretion Enhance the Role of Professionalism in Times of Crisis? A Comparative Policy Analysis of Distance Teaching in Italy and Switzerland during the COVID-19 Pandemic." *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice* 23 (1): 74–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13876988.2020.1844544>.
- Matland, R. E. 1995. "Synthesizing the Implementation Literature: The Ambiguity-Conflict Model of Policy Implementation." *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 5 (2): 145–174.
- Musset, P. 2010. "Initial Teacher Education and Continuing Training Policies in a Comparative Perspective." *OECD Educational Working Papers*, No.48, OECD Publishing, Paris.
- Parkhurst, J. 2017. *The Politics of Evidence*. Abingdon (UK) and New York: Routledge.
- Pupolin, L. 2000. "La Prima Formazione Dei Docenti: quale Percorso?" *Insegnare* 10. Accessed May 15, 2025. https://storico.cidi.it/insegnare/articoli/pupo_01.htm.
- Regonini, G. 2017. "Governmentalities without Policy Capacity." *Policy Sciences* 50 (2): 163–178. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11077-017-9283-3>.
- Sabatier, P., and D. Mazmanian. 1980. "The Implementation of Public Policy: A Framework of Analysis." *Policy Studies Journal* 8 (4): 538–560. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0072.1980.tb01266.x>.
- Sager, F., C. Mavrot, and S. Hadorn. 2015. "Addressing Multilevel Program Complexity by Evaluation Design." *European Policy Analysis* 1 (2): 90–110. <https://doi.org/10.18278/epa.1.2.5>.
- Schneider, A., and H. Ingram. 1988. "Systematically Pinching Ideas: A Comparative Approach to Policy Design." *Journal of Public Policy* 8 (1): 61–80. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0143814X00006851>.
- Symeonidis, V. 2018. "Revisiting the European Teacher Education Area: The Transformation of Teacher Education Policies and Practices in Europe." *Center for Educational Policy Studies Journal* 8 (3): 13–34. <https://doi.org/10.26529/cepsj.509>.
- Tamaro, R., A. Petolicchio, and A. D'Alessio. 2017. "Teacher Training and Recruitment Systems: A Leitmotiv." *Italian Journal of Educational Research* 19: 53–68.
- Virani, A., A. S. Bali, B. Cashore, M. Howlett, and M. Ramesh. 2024. "The Design Roots of Policy Problems: Unpacking the Role of Procedural Tools in Design Fitness and Resilience." *Public Administration* 102 (1): 302–317. <https://doi.org/10.1111/padm.12924>.
- Weiss, C. H. 1997. "How Can Theory-Based Evaluation Make Greater Headway?" *Evaluation Review* 21 (4): 501–524. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0193841X9702100405>.